
Flexible work arrangements and employee performance in international non-governmental organizations: the mediating role of job satisfaction.

Auteur 1 : KABORE Cédric Ghislain.

Auteur 2 : KABORE Rimvie Enoc.

Auteur 3 : BERIYAN Attianbou Bienvenu Binger.

KABORE Cédric Ghislain, ORCID: 0009-0005-8048-1004, PhD, Norbert Zongo University, Koudougou, Burkina Faso,

KABORE Rimvie Enoc, ORCID: 0000-0002-3176-7322, PhD, Daniel Ouézzin Coulibaly University, Dédougou, Burkina Faso,

BERIYAN Attianbou Bienvenu Binger, ORCID: 0009-0005-8838-6677 PhD, Thomas Sankara University, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso,

Déclaration de divulgation : L'auteur n'a pas connaissance de quelconque financement qui pourrait affecter l'objectivité de cette étude.

Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : KABORE, C. G., KABORE, R. E. & BERIYAN, A. B. B (2026) « Flexible work arrangements and employee performance in international non-governmental organizations: the mediating role of job satisfaction », African Scientific Journal « Volume 03, Num 36 » pp: 2258 – 2277.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.20853866

Copyright © 2026 – ASJ

Abstract

This study aims to examine the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance in international non-governmental organizations in Burkina Faso, with particular emphasis on the mediating role of job satisfaction. The study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design based on survey data collected from 234 employees working in international non-governmental organizations. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire and analyzed through partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to test the hypothesized relationships and the mediating effect of job satisfaction. The results indicate that flexible work arrangements do not have a significant direct effect on employee performance. However, they have a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction, which in turn enhances employee performance. The findings further confirm that job satisfaction plays a positive and significant mediating role in the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance. The study suggests that managers should consider flexible work arrangements as a strategic lever to improve employee satisfaction rather than expecting immediate, direct gains in performance. By implementing flexibility practices aligned with employees' needs and promoting work-life balance, organizations can indirectly strengthen employee performance. The integration of job satisfaction indicators into management control systems is also recommended to monitor organizational outcomes better. This research contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence from the underexplored context of international non-governmental organizations in Burkina Faso. It highlights that the effect of flexible work arrangements on employee performance is primarily indirect, operating through job satisfaction, thereby enriching the understanding of these relationships in developing-country contexts.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, flexible work arrangements, employee performance, international non-governmental organizations, structural equation models.

Introduction

In the current era of globalization, organizations face multiple challenges, and human capital constitutes their strategic asset (Fulmer & Ployhart, 2014). To address this issue, it is necessary to keep employees motivated and engaged by creating a work environment conducive to performance while allowing them to maintain a balance between professional and personal life (Rane, 2011). The professional world has undergone significant transformations in recent years, particularly with the emergence of new forms of work such as part-time work and the possibility of adapting work to time and location constraints (Çivilidağ & Durmaz, 2024). Flexible work has therefore become widespread in many countries in recent years (Menezes & Kelliher, 2017). This trend has been strongly accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in developed countries (Çivilidağ & Durmaz, 2024). The health crisis reinforced this dynamic by imposing a reorganization of work environments (Chukwudi et al., 2021).

In Burkina Faso, international non-governmental organizations (INGOs) face numerous socio-economic challenges. They are key actors in the labor market, where job stability and quality of work life have become major concerns. These organizations, often originating from very diverse contexts, must reconcile their humanitarian mission with performance requirements. Thus, the implementation of flexible work arrangements involves both employee satisfaction issues and performance challenges. According to the report on the contribution of Non-Governmental Organizations, Development Associations (NGOs/DAs), and foundations to the development of Burkina Faso by the Ministry of Economy, Finance, and Prospective (2021): “The staff employed by NGOs/DAs and Foundations to implement their development programs consists of salaried employees and volunteer expatriates and nationals.”

Flexible work refers to the possibility for employees to adapt their working hours and workplace. It includes many forms such as teamwork, part-time work, teleworking, flexible or variable schedules, job sharing, seasonal work, annual leave, or annualized working hours (Çivilidağ & Durmaz, 2024). According to Anderson & Kelliher (2009), workplace flexibility refers to the ability to adapt working conditions to employees' personal needs and preferences. This includes schedules, the workplace, working time, or leave. Performance is a polysemous concept that must be contextualized (Renaud & Berland, 2007). In the context of our research, employee performance is linked to what they accomplish or fail to accomplish in their work (Güngör, 2011). A high-performing employee acts in ways that benefit the organization (Doucet et al., 2020, p. 32). Two forms of performance directly related to employee performance are distinguished: task performance, which concerns the execution of duties specified in the job

description, and contextual performance, which encompasses voluntary behaviors aimed at helping colleagues and improving the organization's overall functioning (Sarpkaya & Bayraktar, 2023). Employee performance corresponds to what the organization expects in terms of behaviors and actions over a given period (Motowidlo & Kell, 2012). Finally, according to Paillé (2008), job satisfaction depends on how a person evaluates their job or professional situation. Job satisfaction refers to the pleasure employees derive from their professional activities, as well as the sense of accomplishment they gain from them (Saeed et al., 2014).

The literature shows that flexible work arrangements improve both productivity and employee satisfaction (Kelliher & Anderson, 2008; Konrad & Mangel, 2000). These practices allow for a better balance between professional and personal life, thereby strengthening employee engagement (Chen, 2015). However, most research on this topic has been conducted in developed countries (Govender et al., 2018), underscoring the importance of exploring these issues in developing countries such as Burkina Faso. Moreover, the literature presents contradictory findings regarding the relationships studied, for example, in the studies by Subramaniam et al. (2024) and Jimad et al. (2024).

Recent evidence confirms the need to update this debate. Bloom et al. (2024) based on a randomized experiment on hybrid work, show that hybrid working improves job satisfaction and retention without damaging performance. In addition, Aksoy et al. (2025) show that work-from-home practices have stabilized globally after the pandemic, confirming that flexible working arrangements are no longer merely temporary practices but structural transformations of work organization. These recent findings justify the relevance of analyzing flexible work arrangements in the Burkinabe INGO context.

The objective of this study is to examine how flexible work arrangements affect employee satisfaction and performance within international non-governmental organizations operating in Burkina Faso. More specifically, we first examine whether flexible arrangements directly affect job satisfaction. Next, we analyze how satisfaction may, in turn, influence employee performance. Finally, we investigate whether flexible arrangements improve performance either directly or indirectly through job satisfaction.

To this end, we propose the following main hypothesis: flexible work arrangements enhance employee performance in INGOs in Burkina Faso by increasing job satisfaction, which plays an intermediary role.

The theoretical framework guiding our research is motivation theory (Maslow, 1958; Svinicki & Vogler, 2012; Trépanier et al., 2023; Vroom, 1964). We focus on motivational factors such

as flexible arrangements and their role in satisfaction and performance. We used structural equation modeling (J. Hair & Alamer, 2022; J. F. Hair et al., 2021; Hair Jr et al., 2017), an approach that notably allows the study of mediating effects (Langevin & Mendoza, 2014). A survey of 234 employees was conducted to collect data, which was analyzed using structural equation modeling. The results show that satisfaction mediates the relationship between flexible work arrangements and performance.

The article is structured into several parts: after the introduction, we present the literature review and formulate the hypotheses, based on motivation theory. The second part concerns the methodology used. Finally, the third part presents the results obtained, followed by the conclusion.

1. Literature Review

1.1. Theoretical Literature Review

Our study is grounded in motivation theory (Maslow, 1958; Svinicki & Vogler, 2012; Trépanier et al., 2023; Vroom, 1964). In this research, we focus on motivational factors such as flexible work arrangements and their role in employee satisfaction and performance. Motivation has been approached through several concepts: instinct (Bandhu et al., 2024), psychological process (Bandura, 1993), need satisfaction (Hull, 1943), self-determination (Deci & Ryan, 1985; Gagné et al., 2015; Trépanier et al., 2023), learning (Svinicki & Vogler, 2012), and hygiene factors (Lavoie & Labrecque, 2010).

Lavoie and Labrecque (2010) suggest that motivational factors increase satisfaction and performance. These authors also highlight hygiene factors associated with dissatisfaction. In our study, flexible work arrangements can be interpreted as hygiene factors that may promote satisfaction. According to Bandhu et al. (2024), instinct theory is at the origin of motivation theory. It is based on the idea that certain behaviors are innate, as suggested by Charles Darwin and George Romanes at the end of the nineteenth century. This approach helps explain why flexible work arrangements are relevant within the theoretical framework, as they respond to natural needs embedded within individuals.

Moreover, Bandura (1993) conceptualizes motivation as a mental process that activates different behaviors and influences employees' actions. Hull (1943) argues that motivation arises from the desire to satisfy certain needs and is influenced by incentives, that is, the value assigned to what can satisfy these needs. These incentives may be positive or negative. Thus, the stronger the incentives, the greater the motivation to act in order to obtain pleasure or avoid pain. Motivation can be classified into three main types (Gagné et al., 2015; Trépanier et al.,

2023): intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation. In this context, flexible work arrangements can be viewed as extrinsic factors.

1.2. Hypotheses Development

First, we examine the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance. According to Mas-Machuca et al. (2016), flexibility provides professional autonomy and allows employees to manage their time and work. Employee outcomes improve when autonomy is granted. Flexibility is a determinant of employee well-being. Frimousse et al. (2018) suggest a positive and significant reciprocal effect between workplace well-being and performance. Thus, flexible work arrangements offer this autonomy by allowing employees to choose their schedules and work locations, which can increase their motivation and, consequently, their performance (Çivilidağ & Durmaz, 2024). Mbae et al. (2019) suggest that many organizations adopt flexible work practices to improve work–life balance, which leads to higher employee performance. In this context, we test Hypothesis 1 in international non-governmental organizations based in Burkina Faso, which posits that flexible work arrangements are positively and significantly associated with employee performance.

Next, the relationship between flexible work arrangements and job satisfaction was also analyzed. Many organizations adopt flexible work arrangements because they are perceived as promoting employee satisfaction. According to McNall et al. (2009), flexible work gives employees a sense of enrichment, which translates into greater job satisfaction. Reduced turnover and fewer work–family conflicts are often observed alongside improved job satisfaction (Omondi, 2016). Andrade et al. (2019) encourage employers to implement strategies to improve job satisfaction and work–life balance through flexible arrangements, which not only have a positive impact on organizations but also increase productivity. Wheatley (2017) found in his study that greater job satisfaction is observed among employees who use various flexible arrangements. For Baeza et al. (2018), work flexibility is an important antecedent of job satisfaction in collectivist and developing economies. Burkina Faso is a developing country. In this context, we test Hypothesis 2 in international non-governmental organizations based in Burkina Faso, which posits that flexible work arrangements are positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction.

We also analyzed the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. Baeza et al. (2018) suggest that job satisfaction leads employees to higher productivity. Job satisfaction is undoubtedly one of the key factors in employee motivation and performance (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015). Judge et al. (2001) conducted a meta-analysis combining several

studies and found that the two variables are positively associated. This relationship may vary for several reasons, including the type of organization. The job satisfaction–various factors may influence employee performance link. Moreover, Huang and Van De Vliert (2003) conducted research in other contexts and found that this relationship can vary across contexts. Our context concerns international non-governmental organizations based in Burkina Faso. Accordingly, we test the following hypothesis: Hypothesis 3. The relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance is positive and significant.

Finally, we analyze the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance. Kipkoech (2018) argues that flexible work arrangements enable employees to manage their professional and family responsibilities. This fosters engagement, motivation, and service quality. When employees are motivated by flexibility, satisfaction improves, which in turn improves performance. Focusing on employee well-being and development improves performance by mediating the effect of need satisfaction (Frimousse et al., 2018). In a study on employees' psychological needs, Grenier et al. (2012) suggest that satisfying employee needs increases autonomous motivation, well-being, and performance. Silminawati and Rachmawati (2022) highlight a relationship among flexible work arrangements, job satisfaction, and employee performance. It is therefore possible that flexible work arrangements improve job satisfaction, thereby enhancing employee performance. We therefore test the following hypothesis: Hypothesis 4. Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance, and this effect is positive and significant.

Figure 1. Theoretical model

Source: Authors

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Research design

Research design in management sciences refers to the methodological structure and procedures established to conduct a study. Our research design is primarily cross-sectional (Lee & Lings, 2008), as we collect data at a single point in time and analyze it simultaneously over a specific period.

From an epistemological standpoint, this study is positioned within a post-positivist paradigm. This positioning is justified by the objective of testing theoretically grounded relationships while recognizing that social reality is observed through respondents' perceptions. The mode of reasoning is hypothetico-deductive: hypotheses are formulated from the literature and then tested empirically using survey data. The choice of a quantitative, cross-sectional, and explanatory approach is therefore consistent with the objective of measuring latent constructs and examining direct and mediating effects through PLS-SEM.

This research is based on a survey using a questionnaire capturing respondents' perceptions. The questionnaire is designed using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 7. Dayan Nana (2019) argues that 7-point scales outperform 5-point scales in terms of reliability. The Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of an individual or a group of individuals regarding a phenomenon (Pawirosumarto et al., 2017). In this study, we measure the following phenomena: employee performance (Putri et al., 2021; Robert & Peter, 2010), with eight dimensions, namely work quantity, work quality, job knowledge, creativity, collaboration, reliability, initiative, and personal qualities; job satisfaction (Oehley, 2007), through five dimensions, namely overall satisfaction with the job itself, satisfaction with pay, satisfaction with career development prospects, satisfaction with job security, and satisfaction with relationships with colleagues; flexible work arrangements (Carlson et al., 2010), based on three dimensions, namely schedule flexibility, timing flexibility, and location flexibility; and social desirability (Crowne & Marlowe, 1960), in order to minimize bias related to inaccurate responses. Paulhus (1984) defines social desirability as “the tendency to provide biased responses in a socially approved direction.”

2.2. Data collection and sampling

Pawirosumarto et al. (2017) suggest using the Slovin formula to estimate the minimum sample size from a limited population. Following the formula below, we calculated the sample size:

$$n = N / [1 + N(e)^2]$$

$N = 13,631$ according to the Ministry of Economy, Finance, and Prospective (2021). The value of e is 0.1. Thus, we obtained $99.27 \approx 100$ as the desired minimum sample size.

Data collection consisted of administering a questionnaire via “LimeSurvey” to employees of international non-governmental organizations operating in Burkina Faso. Prior to data collection, we pre-tested the questionnaire with university colleagues and ten (10) professionals working in NGOs. This allowed us to refine the questionnaire. Data collection took place over a period of eight (08) months, from December 2024 to July 2025. The questionnaire was distributed randomly and directly to employees working exclusively at INGOs, enabling us to collect 340 responses. After data processing and outlier removal, we obtained a final sample of 234, well above the minimum sample size.

The sample for this study consists of 234 employees, predominantly male (82.05% of the total workforce), compared with 17.95% female. The age distribution shows a predominance of individuals aged 26 to 35 years (50.43%), followed by those aged 36 to 45 years (39.32%). Young employees aged 20 to 25 years (1.71%) and those aged 46 years and above (8.55%) are underrepresented. The respondents’ education level is generally high: 64.53% hold a master’s degree, 24.79% hold a bachelor’s degree, and 5.56% hold a doctorate. 5.12% have an education level below the baccalaureate.

Regarding organizational tenure, the majority of respondents (73.93%) have worked in their organization for less than five years, while only 9.4% have more than ten years of tenure. In contrast, professional experience in the sector appears more balanced: 32.91% of respondents report between three and five years of experience, and 32.05% report ten years or more.

Employees who participated in the survey come from several departments or units, including monitoring, evaluation, accountability and learning (2.56%), project/program management (11.96%), training (1.28%), IT (2.99%), marketing/communication (5.12%), administrative and financial management (8.97%), procurement and general services (5.98%), human resources (6.41%), general management (12.82%), technical production management (6.83%), research and development (13.24%), supply chain/logistics (2.99%), and finally 18.85% of respondents come from other departments.

3. Results

Following Hair et al. (2021) and Hair Jr. et al. (2017), this study employs multivariate analysis techniques, particularly exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis as well as multiple regression analysis, within the framework of structural equation modeling. This approach is grounded in a variance-based perspective, in contrast to traditional covariance-based

approaches. One of the main advantages of this method lies in its ability to provide robust estimates, even with relatively modest sample sizes. The structural equation modeling approach also allows for rigorous testing of the hypothesized relationships between latent variables (Hair et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the three constructs of the measurement model meet the requirements of convergent and discriminant validity, as well as the criteria for composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha (Hair & Alamer, 2022; Hair et al., 2021). The main empirical results derived from the estimations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation of the reflective measurement model

Variables	Items	Composite Reliability		Convergent validity				95% BCa CI	Decision	
		α	ρ_A	AVE	λ	Item Reliability	t-value			
Flexible Work Arrangements	AT	0.7	0.745	0.753	0.27	0.036	1.72	-0.082; 0.550	Delete	
	F1				9		5		5	
	AT				0.83		15.7		0.709; 0.8	Preserved
	F2				1		65		95	ed
	AT				0.90		27.3		0.850; 0.9	Preserved
F3	5	43	61	ed						
Job Satisfaction	ST1	0.7	0.719	0.51	0.72	0.418	16.1	0.622; 0.8	Preserved	
	ST2				7		57		01	ed
	ST3				0.47		5.32		0.272; 0.6	Delete
	ST4				5		3		21	d
	ST5				0.69		14.1		0.583; 0.7	Preserved
ST3	9	41	78	ed						
ST4	0.68	13.0	0.563; 0.7	Preserved						
ST5	8	64	73	ed						
ST5	0.67	13.4	0.555; 0.7	Preserved						
	9	13	59	ed						

Source: Authors

Performance is modeled as a formative construct based on tetrad analysis, and the VIF values for each item are all below 2. This is also the case for the other two variables, in line with Hair et al. (2021). The data analysis also indicates good discriminant validity according to both the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) matrix and the Fornell–Larcker criterion suggested by J. F. Hair et al. (2021).

We assessed the fit of our structural model, which showed an SRMR of 0.075, below 0.08, indicating a very good model fit. Using 10,000 resamples (bootstrap), the structural model

coefficients and their statistical significance were estimated. Bootstrapping allowed testing of the coefficients across multiple samples.

Hypothesis H1, positing a positive and significant relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance, is not supported ($\beta = 0.024^{ns}$, $t = 0.274$, $f^2 = 0.001$), indicating the absence of a statistically significant effect. In contrast, Hypothesis H2, which states that flexible work arrangements are positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction, is supported ($\beta = 0.331^{***}$, $t = 5.709$, $f^2 = 0.123$), revealing a moderate effect size. Hypothesis H3, according to which job satisfaction is positively and significantly related to employee performance, is also supported ($\beta = 0.568^{***}$, $t = 10.826$, $f^2 = 0.430$), suggesting a large effect. Finally, Hypothesis H4, which postulates a positive and significant mediating effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance, is supported ($\beta = 0.188^{***}$, $t = 4.793$, $f^2 = 0.053$), indicating a small-to-moderate mediation effect.

Figure 2. Structural equation model

Model estimated at the 1% significance level. Legend: ns = not significant; *** = significant at the 1% level.

Source: prepared by the authors.

Source: Authors

4. Discussion

The results of this study present important theoretical and managerial implications. First, the results suggest that, in the context of international NGOs in Burkina Faso, implementing a flexible management system for employees leads to higher levels of overall job satisfaction, consistent with the work of Hyman & Summers (2004) and Kelliher & Anderson (2010). This

is because employees are more engaged when they have some degree of flexibility (Roehling et al., 2001). The results of our research show that the relationship between flexibility and performance can be influenced by intermediary variables (e.g., Bloom et al., 2015; Kelliher & Anderson, 2010), with job satisfaction serving as a mediating variable. In this article, we relied on motivation theory (Maslow, 1958; Svinicki & Vogler, 2012; Trépanier et al., 2023; Vroom, 1964) to conduct this research. Having flexible arrangements, therefore, constitutes a motivational factor that improves employee satisfaction. The results of this study strengthen our theoretical foundation by ruling out a direct link between flexible work arrangements and performance. Hypothesis H4 highlights a positive and significant mediating effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between flexibility and performance. Allen et al. (2013) suggest that the benefits of flexibility practices largely depend on employees' perceptions and their impact on well-being. These results confirm the importance of integrating mediating variables into the analysis of the relationship between flexibility and performance. These findings are also consistent with those of Bloom et al. (2015), who showed that teleworking improved productivity through better satisfaction and reduced stress. Our indicators of flexible work take this aspect into account, depending on the workplace. From a theoretical standpoint, these results are consistent with the work of Locke (1976) on job satisfaction and Herzberg's two-factor theory (1965), according to which the quality of working conditions constitutes a major determinant of motivation and effectiveness.

From a managerial perspective, flexibility constitutes an important motivational lever, as it allows employees to adapt their personal and professional organization, thereby reducing work-life conflicts. The results highlight management control practices and tools, particularly those oriented toward performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017; Tremblay, 2012). Thus, flexible work arrangements are an organizational lever to guide individual behaviors toward performance objectives and organizational sustainability (Gasic et al., 2024). Management controllers can integrate satisfaction as an indicator on their dashboards to gain insight, as it influences performance when flexible work arrangements are in place. Therefore, job satisfaction is an important indicator to be integrated into social dashboards, as proposed by Epstein & Manzoni (1998).

Finally, in this study, the items relating to job satisfaction and flexible work arrangements were carefully selected to measure the latent constructs best. However, two items (ST2 and ATF1) were removed during the analysis to improve the convergent and discriminant validity of the variables (J. Hair & Alamer, 2022; J. F. Hair et al., 2011, 2021; Hair Jr et al., 2017). This

methodological decision reflects the need to ensure the robustness of the measurement model. Four items were retained to measure job satisfaction. Item ST1 highlights the intrinsic aspect of work, linked to internal motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2013). Item ST3 reinforces the developmental perspective of satisfaction. Item ST4 reflects satisfaction with the quality of leadership and organizational support, confirming the importance of managers' roles in employee well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Finally, Item ST5 measures the relational and social dimension of satisfaction, aligning with Locke's (1976) work, which emphasized that the quality of interpersonal relationships at work is a major determinant of overall satisfaction. In contrast, item ST2, related to salary, was removed. Several reasons can explain this exclusion. First, in the context of international NGOs in Burkina Faso, remuneration is often governed by standardized salary scales, which limit perceived variability among employees. Second, salary constitutes a hygiene factor according to Herzberg (1965). It can reduce dissatisfaction but is not necessarily a strong predictor of satisfaction. Thus, its statistical weight in constructing the satisfaction variable may be limited, which justifies its removal to strengthen model coherence. Two items were retained to measure flexibility. Therefore, the two determining items of flexible work arrangements in Burkina Faso are the temporal dimension, which can improve work-life balance (Hill et al., 2001), and the spatial dimension of flexibility, linked to telework or hybrid work practices. In contrast, item ATF1 was removed based on data analysis suggested by Hair & Alamer (2022), Hair et al. (2011, 2021), and Hair Jr. et al. (2017). This decision is relevant because irregular working hours may be perceived as "imposed flexibility," a form of constraint generating stress or dissatisfaction. Several authors (Kossek & Michel, 2011) have emphasized that the distinction between "chosen flexibility" and "imposed flexibility" is essential: only the former promotes satisfaction and performance. The exclusion of this item, therefore, makes it possible to better target the true nature of flexibility under study.

Conclusion

We examined flexible work arrangements and employee performance in international non-governmental organizations. The objective of this research was to analyze the relationship between job satisfaction, flexible work arrangements, and employee performance in international non-governmental organizations operating in Burkina Faso. The relationship between work flexibility and employee performance has been widely explored in the international literature but remains under-documented in the Burkinabè context, particularly within international non-governmental organizations. Drawing on motivation theory, this study, using a sample of 234 employees and structural equation modeling, analyzed the effect of flexible work arrangements on performance by examining the mediating role of job satisfaction. The results reveal that there is no significant direct effect between flexibility and employee performance. However, flexibility is positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction, which in turn influences employee performance. Moreover, job satisfaction plays a positive and significant mediating role, confirming that the impact of flexibility on performance operates primarily indirectly.

From a managerial perspective, these findings suggest that leaders of international NGOs should consider flexible work arrangements as a strategic lever for well-being and motivation rather than merely an organizational tool. Implementing mechanisms adapted to operational constraints and supported by policies of support, recognition, and communication could thus transform flexibility into a driver of performance.

Finally, the limitations inherent in the cross-sectional nature of the data and the specific context of international NGOs open avenues for future longitudinal and comparative research in other sectors and regions to confirm and generalize these conclusions. Our study does not incorporate certain variables that could have enriched the analysis, such as employee engagement (Gasic et al., 2024; Locke, 1968), productivity (Febriana & Mujib, 2024), or moderating variables such as role and work tensions (Kahn et al., 1964; Rizzo et al., 1970). Likewise, other relevant dimensions, such as environmental uncertainty (Duncan, 1972) or the use of information technologies for communication (Andersen, 2001), were not considered. These factors may influence the relationship examined. Future research could therefore integrate these variables to explore new explanatory avenues. Nevertheless, the absence of these dimensions does not weaken the quality of our study, as it aims to address a specific research question aligned with the theoretical framework employed.

Bibliography

- Aksoy, C. G., Barrero, J. M., Bloom, N., Davis, S. J., Dolls, M., & Zarate, P. (2025). The global persistence of work from home. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 122(27), e2509892122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2509892122>
- Allen, T. D., Johnson, R. C., Kiburz, K. M., & Shockley, K. M. (2013). Work–Family Conflict and Flexible Work Arrangements : Deconstructing Flexibility. *Personnel Psychology*, 66(2), 345-376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12012>
- Andersen, T. J. (2001). Information technology, strategic decision making approaches and organizational performance in different industrial settings. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 10(2), 101-119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687\(01\)00043-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687(01)00043-9)
- Anderson, D., & Kelliher, C. (2009). Flexible working and engagement : The importance of choice. *Strategic HR Review*, 8(2), 13-18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14754390910937530>
- Andrade, M. S., Westover, J. H., & Kupka, B. A. (2019). The role of work-life balance and worker scheduling flexibility in predicting global comparative job satisfaction. *database*, 9(2), 80-105.
- Baeza, M. A., Gonzalez, J. A., & Wang, Y. (2018). Job flexibility and job satisfaction among Mexican professionals : A socio-cultural explanation. *Employee Relations*, 40(5), 921-942.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2017). Job demands–resources theory : Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 22(3), 273.
- Bandhu, D., Mohan, M. M., Nittala, N. A. P., Jadhav, P., Bhadauria, A., & Saxena, K. K. (2024). Theories of motivation : A comprehensive analysis of human behavior drivers. *Acta Psychologica*, 244, 104177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104177>
- Bandura, A. (1993). La théorie sociale-cognitive des buts. *Revue québécoise de psychologie*, 14(2).
- Bloom, N., Liang, J., Roberts, J., & Ying, Z. J. (2015). Does Working from Home Work? Evidence from a Chinese Experiment. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 130(1), 165-218. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qju032>
- Bloom, N., Han, R., & Liang, J. (2024). Hybrid working from home improves retention without damaging performance. *Nature*, 630, 920-925.
- Carlson, D. S., Grzywacz, J. G., & Michele Kacmar, K. (2010). The relationship of schedule flexibility and outcomes via the work-family interface. *Journal of managerial psychology*, 25(4), 330-355.

- Chen, Y. (2015). *The link between flexible work arrangements and employee work outcomes : A multilevel model*. Rutgers The State University of New Jersey, School of Graduate Studies.
- Chukwudi, C. G., O, P. U., & N, O. A. (2021). Flexible work arrangement and employees' performance during COVID-19 era in selected micro-finance banks in Enugu state. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 12(6), 195-203.
- Çivilidağ, A., & Durmaz, Ş. (2024). Examining the relationship between flexible working arrangements and employee performance : A mini review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1398309. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1398309>
- Crowne, D. P., & Marlowe, D. (1960). A new scale of social desirability independent of psychopathology. *Journal of consulting psychology*, 24(4), 349.
- Dayan Nana, A. (2019). *Comparaison des échelles de mesure de l'utilisabilité*. Université de Sherbrooke.
- De Menezes, L. M., & Kelliher, C. (2017). Flexible Working, Individual Performance, and Employee Attitudes : Comparing Formal and Informal Arrangements. *Human Resource Management*, 56(6), 1051-1070. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21822>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). The general causality orientations scale : Self-determination in personality. *Journal of research in personality*, 19(2), 109-134.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2013). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Doucet, O., Lapalme, M.-È., Morin, D., & Fortin-Bergeron, C. (2020). *Gérer la performance des employés au travail*. Editions JFD.
- Duncan, R. B. (1972). Characteristics of organizational environments and perceived environmental uncertainty. *Administrative science quarterly*, 313-327.
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 71(3), 500.
- Epstein, M., & Manzoni, J.-F. (1998). Implementing corporate strategy : From Tableaux de Bord to balanced scorecards. *European management journal*, 16(2), 190-203.
- Febriana, A., & Mujib, M. (2024). Increasing Productivity of Gen Z Employees : The Role of Flexible Work Arrangements and Participative Style. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 22, a2489. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v22i0.2489>
- Frimousse, S., Swalhi, A., Giraud, L., Peretti, J.-M., & Baloi, I.-C. (2018). Favoriser la performance adaptative via le développement RH dans un contexte de changement permanent :

- Le cas de Ford Roumanie. *Management international*, 22(4), 39-52. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1060836ar>
- Fulmer, I. S., & Ployhart, R. E. (2014). "Our Most Important Asset": A Multidisciplinary/Multilevel Review of Human Capital Valuation for Research and Practice. *Journal of Management*, 40(1), 161-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206313511271>
- Gagné, M., Forest, J., Vansteenkiste, M., Crevier-Braud, L., Van den Broeck, A., Aspley, A. K., ... Güntert, S. T. (2015). The Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale : Validation evidence in seven languages and nine countries. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 24(2), 178-196.
- Gasic, D., Berber, N., Slavic, A., Jelaca, M. S., Maric, S., Bjekic, R., & Aleksic, M. (2024). The Key Role of Employee Commitment in the Relationship Between Flexible Work Arrangements and Employee Behavior. *Sustainability*, 16(22), 10067. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su162210067>
- Gasic, D., Jevtic, T., Berber, N., & Aleksic, M. (2025). Job Satisfaction, Flexible Work Arrangements and Innovative Work Behavior in Serbian SMEs. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 16(1), 40-51. <https://doi.org/10.24867/IJIEM-369>
- Govender, L., Migiro, S. O., & Kyule, A. K. (2018). Flexible work arrangements, job satisfaction and performance. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 10(3), 268-277. <https://doi.org/10.22610/jeb.v10i3.2333>
- Grenier, S., Chiochio, F., & Beaulieu, G. (2012). Évaluation du rendement et motivation au travail : Propositions de recherche pour une rétroaction sur le rendement qui favorise la satisfaction des besoins psychologiques fondamentaux. *Management international*, 16(4), 169-179. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1013156ar>
- Güngör, P. (2011). The relationship between reward management system and employee performance with the mediating role of motivation : A quantitative study on global banks. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 24, 1510-1520.
- Hair, J., & Alamer, A. (2022). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in second language and education research : Guidelines using an applied example. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, 1(3), 100027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2022.100027>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R: A Workbook*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7>

- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM : Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Gudergan, S. P. (2017). *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*. Sage Publications.
- Herzberg, F. (1965). The motivation to work among Finnish supervisors. *Personnel psychology*, 18(4).
- Hill, E. J., Hawkins, A. J., Ferris, M., & Weitzman, M. (2001). Finding an Extra Day a Week : The Positive Influence of Perceived Job Flexibility on Work and Family Life Balance. *Family Relations*, 50(1), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3729.2001.00049.x>
- Huang, X., & Van De Vliert, E. (2003). Where intrinsic job satisfaction fails to work : National moderators of intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24(2), 159-179. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.186>
- Hull, C. L. (1943). *Principles of behavior : An introduction to behavior theory*.
- Hyman, J., & Summers, J. (2004). Lacking balance? Work-life employment practices in the modern economy. *Personnel Review*, 33(4), 418-429.
- Jimad, H., Roslina, R., & Yuningsih, Y. (2024). The effect of flexible working arrangements on educator performance in Indonesia. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 38(7), 1944-1958. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-12-2023-0631>
- Judge, T. A., Thoresen, C. J., Bono, J. E., & Patton, G. K. (2001). The job satisfaction–job performance relationship : A qualitative and quantitative review. *Psychological bulletin*, 127(3), 376.
- Kahn, R. L., Wolfe, D. M., Quinn, R. P., Snoek, J. D., & Rosenthal, R. A. (1964). *Organizational stress : Studies in role conflict and ambiguity*.
- Kelliher, C., & Anderson, D. (2008). For better or for worse? An analysis of how flexible working practices influence employees' perceptions of job quality. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19(3), 419-431. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190801895502>
- Kelliher, C., & Anderson, D. (2010). Doing more with less? Flexible working practices and the intensification of work. *Human Relations*, 63(1), 83-106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726709349199>
- Kipkoech, K. V. (2018). *Flexible working arrangements on employee performance in Kericho County Referral Hospital, Kenya*. Research Project, Kenyatta University.

- Konrad, A. M., & Mangel, R. (2000). The impact of work-life programs on firm productivity. *Strategic Management Journal*, 21(12), 1225-1237.
- Kossek, E. E., & Michel, J. S. (2011). *Flexible work schedules*.
- Langevin, P., & Mendoza, C. (2014). Impliquer les managers à atteindre leurs objectifs : Participation, feedback et confiance. *Comptabilité - Contrôle - Audit*, Tome 20(3), 43-71.
- Lavoie, A.-M., & Labrecque, M. (2010). Evaluation d'une situation conflictuelle entre deux services dans un centre d'hébergement de personnes âgées selon la théorie de Herzberg. *Recherche en soins infirmiers*, 103(4), 92-98.
- Lee, N., & Lings, I. (2008). *Doing business research : A guide to theory and practice*. SAGE.
- Locke, E. A. (1968). Toward a theory of task motivation and incentives. *Organizational behavior and human performance*, 3(2), 157-189.
- Locke, E. A. (1976). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*.
- Maslow, A. H. (1958). *A Dynamic Theory of Human Motivation*.
- Mas-Machuca, M., Berbegal-Mirabent, J., & Alegre, I. (2016). Work-life balance and its relationship with organizational pride and job satisfaction. *Journal of managerial psychology*, 31(2), 586-602.
- Mbae, C., Ogolla, D., & Mbebe, J. (2019). Effect of flexible work practices on employee performance in electricity generating companies in Kenya. *Journal of International Business, Innovation and Strategic Management*, 3(3), 16-34.
- McNall, L. A., Masuda, A. D., & Nicklin, J. M. (2009). Flexible Work Arrangements, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intentions : The Mediating Role of Work-to-Family Enrichment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 144(1), 61-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980903356073>
- Ministère de l'économie, des finances et de la prospective. (2021). *Contribution des ONG/AD et Fondations au renforcement de l'action humanitaire au Burkina Faso : État des lieux, défis et perspectives*.
- Motowidlo, S. J., & Kell, H. J. (2012). *Job Performance. Handb. Psychol.* Wiley Hoboken, NJ.
- Muga, I. O., & Senelwa, A. (2022). Influence of flexibility work practice and employee performance in public health sector in Kenya. *Int. J. Soc. Sci. Inform. Technol*, 8, 40-50.
- Oehley, A.-M. (2007). *The development and evaluation of a partial talent management competency model* [PhD Thesis, University of Stellenbosch].
- Omondi, A. A. (2016). *Flexible Work Schedules-a Critical Review of Literature* [PhD Thesis, University of Nairobi].

- Paillé, P. (2008). Les comportements de citoyenneté organisationnelle : Une étude empirique sur les relations avec l'engagement affectif, la satisfaction au travail et l'implication au travail. *Le travail humain*, 71(1), 22-42. <https://doi.org/10.3917/th.711.0022>
- Paulhus, D. L. (1984). Two-component models of socially desirable responding. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 46(3), 598.
- Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K., & Muchtar, M. (2017). Factors affecting employee performance of PT. Kiyokuni Indonesia. *International journal of law and management*, 59(4), 602-614.
- Putri, L. E., Rimawan, E., & Setyadi, A. (2021). The Relationship of Job Satisfaction, Flexible Working Arrangements and Employee Performance using SEM-PLS and FIMIX-PLS : A Case Study of Employees in Insurance Company. *NVEO-NATURAL VOLATILES & ESSENTIAL OILS Journal*, 11978-11991.
- Rane, D. B. (2011). Employee job satisfaction : An essence of organization. *HRM Review*, 11(7), 10-16.
- Raziq, A., & Maulabakhsh, R. (2015). Impact of Working Environment on Job Satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 717-725. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00524-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00524-9)
- Renaud, A., & Berland, N. (2007). Mesure de la performance globale des entreprises. *Comptabilité et environnement*, CD-Rom.
- Rizzo, J. R., House, R. J., & Lirtzman, S. I. (1970). Role conflict and ambiguity in complex organizations. *Administrative science quarterly*, 150-163.
- Robert, V., & Peter, O. (2010). *Organisation of working time : Implications for productivity and working conditions*. Netherlands.
- Roehling, P. V., Roehling, M. V., & Moen, P. (2001). The Relationship Between Work-Life Policies and Practices and Employee Loyalty : A Life Course Perspective. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 22(2), 141-170. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016630229628>
- Saeed, I., Waseem, M., Sikander, S., & Rizwan, M. (2014). The relationship of turnover intention with job satisfaction, job performance, leader member exchange, emotional intelligence and organizational commitment. *International journal of learning and development*, 4(2), 242-256.
- Sarpkaya, E., & Bayraktar, O. (2023). The Effect of Flexible Working on Job Performance During the Covid 19 Pandemic : The Mediation Role of Job Characteristics. *Uluslararası Ekonomi İşletme ve Politika Dergisi*, 7(2), 367-386. <https://doi.org/10.29216/ueip.1295399>

- Silminawati, A., & Rachmawati, R. (2022). *The Influence of Flexible Working Arrangements on Work Life Balance, and Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as Mediator*.
- Subramaniam, G., Abd Rahman, S. A. B., Dass, L. C., & Meng, W. (2024). The Impact of Flexible Working Arrangements on Employee Outcomes Pre-Covid in Malaysia. *SMART-Journal of Business Management Studies*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.34293/2321-2012.2024.0002.10>
- Svinicki, M. D., & Vogler, J. S. (2012). Motivation and Learning: Modern Theories. In N. M. Seel (Éd.), *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning* (p. 2336-2339). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_392
- Tremblay, J.-F. (2012). Les indicateurs non financiers dacharns la littérature scientifique du contrôle de gestion : Un bilan. *Comptabilités et innovation*, CD-Rom.
- Trépanier, S.-G., Peterson, C., Gagné, M., Fernet, C., Levesque-Côté, J., & Howard, J. L. (2023). Revisiting the Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS). *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 32(2) , 157-172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2022.2116315>
- Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and motivation*.
- Wheatley, D. (2017). Employee satisfaction and use of flexible working arrangements. *Work, Employment and Society*, 31(4), 567-585. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017016631447>